

Second Dissociation Constant of Phosphoric Acid : A Recalculation from Alkaline Solutions Using Modified Davies Equation

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The second dissociation constant of phosphoric acid in alkaline solution has been recalculated from the e.m.f. data of Bates and Acree from 0° to 50° in steps of 5°, using modified Davies equation. At each temperature the recalculated value of pK_2 closely agrees with the pK_2 value given by Bates and Acree.

Our method of determining pK value of acids is accurate as well as simpler.

DAVIES equation¹ has been widely used to find out the dissociation constant of a large number of electrolytes in aqueous solution. Recently Prasad² has shown that Davies equation is not correct. It has been shown in a number of communications from this laboratory³⁻⁵ that B_1 in equation (1),

$$\log \gamma_1 = \frac{-AZ_1^2 \sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} + B_1 \mu \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

is independent of the composition of the ionic atmosphere, except in those cases where there is a drastic change in the composition (say, from acidic to alkaline) of the ionic atmosphere.

Harned and coworkers⁶⁻¹⁰ have measured the value of K_w from cells of the type (C-1), where $M = Li^+, Na^+, K^+, Cs^+$ and Ba^{2+} .

They have taken the activity coefficient of water into account. The activity coefficient of water in a solution of ionic strength 0.1 is about 0.996. Hence we have taken the activity coefficient of water as unity and have recalculated the value of K_w . The e.m.f. of cell (C-1) then will be given by equation

$$(2), \text{ where } k = 2.3026 \frac{RT}{F}.$$

$$\frac{(E - E^\circ)}{k} + \log \frac{m_2}{m_1} = pK_w - (B_{Cl} - B_{OH})\mu \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

If our idea, that B_1 in equation (1) is independent of the composition of ionic atmosphere is correct, then in the case of alkaline solutions, where the same alkali together with its chloride is used, $(B_{Cl} - B_{OH})$ should be constant irrespective of

the ratio of alkali to chloride and the presence or absence of additional ions, because in all the solutions OH^- ion is surrounded by the same alkali ion and so is the case of Cl^- ion.

In case of any cell of type (C-1), all the quantities on the left-hand side of equation (2) are known. When the L.H.S. of equation (2) is plotted against μ , the plots¹¹ are found to be straight lines (indicating a constancy of $B_{Cl} - B_{OH}$, vis-a-vis μ) but having different slopes. The slopes differ as in each case the ionic atmosphere is different, being composed of a particular M ion. The intercept in each case gives pK_w . The recalculated pK_w values and the values of $(B_{Cl} - B_{OH})$, where $M = Na^+$, at temperature 0° to 50° in steps of 5° are recorded in Table 1. It may be noted that wherever e.m.f. values occurred in int. volt we have converted them in abs. volt before using them in equation (2).

TABLE 1—VALUES OF $(B_{Cl} - B_{OH})$ AND pK_w FROM 0° TO 50°C, WHERE $M = Na^+$

Temp. in °C	pK_w	$(B_{Cl} - B_{OH})$
0	14.947	0.064
5	14.736	0.054
10	14.538	0.046
15	14.350	0.042
20	14.170	0.025
25	14.002	0.027
30	13.842	0.027
35	13.690	0.026
40	13.462	0.021
45	13.398	0.024
50	13.263	0.012

Bates and Acree¹² determined the second dissociation constant of phosphoric acid from 0° to 6° in steps of 5° using cell (C-2).

They worked with buffer solutions having ionic strength *ca.* 0.02 to 0.6) and having three different ratios of $\frac{m_3}{m_4}$ viz., 1.0132, 1.5684 and 0.6540. Some of

the cell solutions having $\frac{m_3}{m_4} = 0.6540$, were alkaline.

In these solutions all the three electrolytes NaH_2PO_4 , Na_2HPO_4 and $NaCl$ are completely dissociated and HPO_4^{2-} suffers hydrolysis as under,

$$So, m_{H_2PO_4} = m_3 + m_{OH}$$

$$m_{HPO_4} = m_4 - m_{OH}$$

$$and, \frac{m_{H_2PO_4} \times m_{OH}}{m_{HPO_4}} = \frac{(m_3 + m_{OH}) \cdot m_{OH}}{(m_4 - m_{OH})} = K_H$$

$$Now, K_h = \frac{a_{H_2PO_4} \times a_{OH}}{a_{HPO_4}} = K_H \times \frac{\gamma_{H_2PO_4} \times \gamma_{OH}}{\gamma_{HPO_4}}$$

$$or, \log K_H + \frac{2A \sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} = \log K_h + B_1 \mu \dots \dots (4)$$

In the above discussion charges have been left out for the sake of typographical neatness. This, however, causes no ambiguity.

Since in cell (C-2) we have the same electrodes and the same kind of equilibrium, the e.m.f. of cell (C-2) will be given by equation (2) as in the case of cell (C-1). The ionic strength of the cell solution used in cell (C-2) is given by equation (5).

$$\mu = m_3 + 3m_4 + m_5 - m_{OH} \dots \dots (5)$$

Using a rough value of μ given by equation (6),

$$\mu \triangleq m_3 + 3m_4 + m_5 \dots \dots (6)$$

and putting $(B_{Cl} - B_{OH})$ and pK_w values recorded in Table 1 in equation (2), we get a value of m_{OH} ($=m_1$). Using this value of m_{OH} in equation (5), a more accurate value of μ is obtained. One iteration is enough to get a constant (and correct) value of μ ; and hence the correct value of m_{OH} is obtained.

A plot of the L.H.S. of equation (4) against μ (up to 0.17) at each temperature is found to be a straight line. The intercept of the plots at $\mu=0$ gives the value of pK_h . pK_h values have also been calculated by standard statistical methods and are shown in Table 2. Now, $pK_h = pK_w - pK_a$, and hence we get the values of pK_a . These values of pK_a as also the values given by Bates and Acree and obtained by rather laborious process are also recorded in Table 2.

TABLE 2—VALUES OF pK_h AND pK_a FROM 0° TO 50°C

Temp. in °C	pK_h		pK_a	
	Graphically	Statistically	Ours	Bates and Acree
0	7.638	7.637	7.312	7.314
5	7.455	7.456	7.281	7.281
10	7.285	7.285	7.253	7.254
15	7.120	7.119	7.230	7.230
20	6.957	6.957	7.213	7.213
25	6.802	6.803	7.200	7.198
30	6.646	6.646	7.195	7.190
35	6.500	6.502	7.189	7.185
40	6.278	6.278	7.184	7.182
45	6.213	6.213	7.185	7.181
50	6.076	6.076	7.187	7.184

It will be seen from the table that at each temperature the two pK_a values agree closely, only at 30°, 35° and 45° the difference goes up to 0.005. The pK_a values recalculated from Bates' data in acidic solution using modified Davies equation also closely agrees with the pK_a values given by Bates.

It may therefore be taken that the modified Davies equation is valid in alkaline solution as well, provided there is no drastic change in the composition of the ionic atmosphere. Our method of calculating pK is simpler and it is now apparent that it is accurate too.

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